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RIGHT TO WEAR HIJAB: LEGAL INTERPRETATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The hijab and other forms of Islamic dress have become a much discussed and controversial issue since recent times especially after the ban on hijab by French legislation in certain spheres and the discussion and debate that subsequently surrounded it. The study focuses on the wearing of the hijab, throughout the world and looks at the reasoning why Muslim women choose to cover or not cover their body and heads. Most women described wearing or not wearing hijab as their choice, although some had more influence from others and rest relies on the text of Quran and Hadith. This paper critically examines the interpretation of Quran and judicial approach towards hijab.

KEYWORDS: *Muhaajaba; Awrah; Zinat; Hijab Shara'ee; Mahrem; Bid'ah*

INTRODUCTION

Hijab is an Arabic term meaning barrier or partition. In the Qur'an, the term 'hijab' refers to a partition or curtain in the literal or metaphorical sense. The verse where it is used literally is commonly understood to refer to the curtain separating visitors to Prophet Muhammad's house from his wives' lodgings. This had led some to argue that the mandate of the Qur'an to wear hijab applied to the wives of Prophet Muhammad, and not women generally¹. However, in Islam, it has broader interpretations. A woman who wears hijab is called Muhaajaba. Fundamentally, hijab is an Islamic cultural dress code which Muslim women should observe in public and some specific private domain. In Islamic culture, dress code for both man and women has special significance and the principle of modesty and chivalry are always appreciated and honoured.

El Guindi, Fadwa; Sherifa Zahur² points out different types of hijab and its nomenclature in the context of cultural and geographical location that inter alia includes *Abaya, Al-amira, Bushiyya, Bukhnuk*, (Eastern Arabia), *Batula* (United Arab Emirates, Oman, Qatar and Southern Iran), *Burqa or Chadari* (Central Asia), *Chador, Dupatta, Nikab* (India and Pakistan), *Elechek* (Kyrgyzstan), *Hijab, Jilbab, Kerudung* (Malaysia), *Khimar, Kimeshek*

¹ Leila Ahmed, *Women and Gender in Islam: Historical Roots of a Modern Debate*, Yale University Press, (1992) 296 pages

² El Guindi, Fadwa; Sherifa Zahur, "Hijab" *The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Islamic World*, Oxford University Press, (2009)

(Kazakhstan, Karakalpakstan and Kyrgyzstan), *Mukena* (Indonesia), *Niqab*, *Paranja* (Uzbek and Tajakistan), *Selendang* (Indonesia), *Shayla* (Arab states of the Persian Gulf).

Nikab is one-piece *Balto* and two-piece *Sharsharf* are loose-falling, full-length garments that serve as overcoats. The Abaya is also full-length, but is more form-fitting and is made of a slightly thinner material.

Rules of modesty according to five different Islamic schools of law suggest that ‘*Awrah*’³ in Arabic is a term used within Islam which denotes the intimate parts of the body, for both men and women, which must be covered with clothing. Exposing the ‘*Awrah*’ is unlawful in Islam and is regarded as sin. According to Holy Quran obscenity originates from wickedness and ignobility. It is either motivated by the intention of harming others or is a habit acquired from socializing with evil and debauched people, who are accustomed to insulting others⁴.

There exists a debate on how much of the male or female body should be covered? While educated, westernised Muslim women prefer to wear a head scarf, the illiterate and rural women wear Burka and Hijab. Women Politicians and Ministers from Asian subcontinent wear head scarf.⁵ However, most Muslim sports women and film celebrities do not prefer to wear hijab.

HOLY QURAN AND BASIS OF HIJAB

As the whole idea of wearing Hijab emanates from the direct instructions of Qur’an, let’s first take a look at a few Ayats from the Holy Scriptures.

There are three verses in Sura An-Nur:-

“Say unto the believer men that they cast down their gaze and guard their private parts; that is purer for them. Verily, Allah is well aware of all that you do.”

“And say unto the believing women that they cast down their gaze and guard their private parts, and they display not their “Zinat” (adornment) except what becomes apparent of it; and they draw their “Khumur” (head covers) over their “Juyub” (neck-slits); and they display not their “Zinat” except to their husbands, or their fathers, or the father of their husbands.....”⁶

The 3rd verse in the same Sura exempts a very old woman from putting on veil:-

“Such elderly women as are past the prospect of marriage, there is no blame on them if they lay aside their outer garments, provided they make not a display of their adornment; but it is good for them if they restrain themselves; and Allah is All-hearing All-knowing.”⁷

³ <http://islamic-dictionary.tumblr.com/post/5658467793/awrah-arabic>

⁴ Qur’an 4:148; Qur’an 33:19

⁵ Late Benzir Bhutto, the Prime Minister of Pakistan, Mrs Khaleda Zia former Prime Minister of Bangladesh and Mrs Mehbooba Mufti Sayeed the current Chief Minister of Jammu and Kashmir use separate head scarf. But, Tansu Çiller (Prime Minister of Turkey), Sheikh Hasina (Current Prime Minister of Bangladesh), Megawati Sukarnoputri (President of Indonesia), and Roza Otunbayeva (President of Kyrgyzstan) and Ameenah Gurib (President of Mauritius) do not use Hijab to cover their head

⁶ Holy Quran, 24: 30-31

⁷ Holy Quran, 24: 60

From the above verses it appears that there are 2 aspect of Hijab:

1. *Hijab of Eyes.*
2. *Hijab of Dress.*

Views of few scholars and researcher is: The holy Quran does not suggest that women should be veiled or they should be kept apart from the world of men. On the contrary, the Qur'an is insistent on the full participation of women in society and in the religious practices. To wear the Hijab is certainly not an Islamic obligatory on women. It is an innovation (Bid'ah) of men suffering from a piety complex who are so weak spiritually that they just cannot trust themselves.⁸

RIGHT TO WEAR HIJAB VIS A VIS MUNICIPAL LAWS

While in some nations wearing Hijab is permissible but in others countries they are regulated.

France: France was the first country in Europe to ban Islamic face veils, such as the Burka and the Niqab in public places. The controversial ban took effect in April 2011 and made it illegal for Muslim women to leave their homes with their faces covered. Women can be fined for wearing a face veil, while anyone who uses threats and violence to forces a woman to wear a veil risks a €30,000 fine and a year in prison.

In July 2014 the European Court of Human Rights upheld the ban. A number of French seaside towns have now also banned the burkini.

Belgium: Belgium was the second European country after France to introduce a ban on full face veils, which outlawed the Burka and Niqab in public areas. Women who cover their faces in public places like streets and parks can be fined and sentenced to up to seven days in jail. The ban came into effect in July 2011.

Bulgaria: Bulgaria's parliament banned the Burka in September 2016 in a bid to boost security in the wake of Islamist militant attacks in Europe. The new law, which bans women from wearing full-face veils in public, was driven by Bulgaria's nationalist Patriotic Front coalition. The party's co-leader Krasimir Karakachanov highlighted the security rationale, adding: "The Burqa is more a uniform than a religious symbol".

Egypt: The Egyptian government has drafted a bill to ban the Niqab and Burka in public places and government institutions. The legislation comes after Egypt's Cairo University banned academic staff from wearing the Niqab in classrooms to make it easier to communicate with students.

Switzerland: A majority of the electorate in the Swiss region of Ticino voted in favour of a ban on face veils in public areas in 2013. The ban came into force in 2016. Muslim women who wear the veil in shops, restaurants or public buildings can be fined up to €9,200 (£7,890).

Italy: Lombardy, the wealthiest region in Italy, approved a ban on women wearing the Burka in hospitals and local government buildings in December 2015. It was the first time an Italian

⁸ Ibrahim B. Syed, Is Hijab Compulsory? Islamic Research Foundation International, Inc.
http://www.irfi.org/articles/articles_1_50/is_hijab_compulsory.htm

region explicitly outlawed Islamic face coverings. Existing laws already prohibit helmets and clothing that make identification difficult in public.

Chad: Chad banned women from wearing the full-face veil following two suicide bomb attacks in June 2015.

There are similar bans in parts of Cameroon and Niger as well as Congo-Brazzaville and the Gabon.⁹

Iran: Iran went from banning all types of veils in 1936 to restoring original dress code between 1980 and 1984. Practical decisions started with the Iranian Cultural Revolution in April 1980, when it was decided that women in government offices and educational institutions would observe the veil.¹⁰ The 1983 penal code of Iran prescribed punishment of 74 lashes for women appearing in public without Islamic hijab (hijab shar'ee).¹¹

Saudi Arab: The Saudi Arabia law requires Muslim women to cover their hair and all women have to wear a full-body garment. These regulations are enforced by the religious police and vigilantes. In 2002 the Saudi religious police were accused by Saudi and international press of hindering the rescue of schoolgirls from a fire because they were not wearing hijab, which resulted in 15 deaths.¹²

JUDICIAL APPROACH(NATIONAL AND INTERNATIONAL) TOWARDS RIGHT TO WEAR HIJAB

In *Nadha Raheem v. Central Board of Secondary, New Delhi*¹³, Two female students belonging to Muslim community contending that the dress code prescribed by the Central Board of Secondary Education (C.B.S.E) of wearing half sleeve kurta/salvar would prejudice them, in so far as their religious custom mandate them to wear a head scarf and also full sleeve dresses. The High Court refused to issue a blanket order and directed that the petitioners who desires to wear a dress according to their religious custom, but contrary to the dress code prescribed by institution, shall present themselves before the Invigilator half an hour before the examination and on any suspicion expressed by the Invigilator, shall also subject themselves to any acceptable mode of personal examination as decided by the Invigilator, but however this invigilation should be carried on only by an authorised person of the same sex. If the Invigilator requires the head scarf or the full sleeve garments to be removed and examined, then the petitioners shall also subject themselves to that, by the authorised person. It is also desirable that the C.B.S.E, issue general instructions to its Invigilators to ensure that religions sentiments be not hurt and at the same time discipline be not compromised.

⁹ <http://www.express.co.uk/news/world/652842/Burka-Niqab-Islamic-Face-veil-Ban-UK-Fine-France-Belgium-Netherlands-Europe-Muslim-dress>

¹⁰ Ramezani, Reza (spring 2007). Hijab dar Iran az Enqelab-e Eslami ta payan Jang-e Tahmili [Hijab in Iran from the Islamic Revolution to the end of the Imposed war] (Persian), Fasnamah-e Takhassusi-ye Banuvan-e Shi'ah [Quarterly Journal of Shiite Women] 11, Qom: Muassasah-e Shi'ah Shinasi, pp. 251-300

¹¹ Elizabeth M. Bucar (2011). Creative Conformity: The Feminist Politics of U.S. Catholic and Iranian Shi'i Women. Georgetown University Press. p. 118; See (Islamic Penal Code), 102 (article 102)". Islamic Parliament Research Center

¹² Saudi Arabia's dress code for women", *The Economist*. Jan 28, 2015; "Saudi police 'stopped' fire rescue". BBC. March 15, 2002

¹³ WP(C).No. 21696 of 2015 (J), The High Court of Kerala, Decided on 9th July, 2015

In *M.Ajmal Khan v The Election Commission of India*¹⁴ the petitioner contended that publication of Muslim Women's photo in electoral roll is violative to Article 25 of the Constitution of India. But the Court refused to accept the petitioner's view.

On 12 February 2003, *Samira Achbita*, a Muslim, was employed as a receptionist by G4S, a private undertaking which provides inter alia, reception services for customers in both the public and private sectors. At the time of Ms Achbita's recruitment there was an unwritten rule within G4S that prohibited employees from wearing visible signs of their political, philosophical or religious beliefs in the workplace.

In April 2006, Ms Achbita informed her employer that she intended to wear an Islamic headscarf during working hours. In response, the management of G4S informed her that the wearing of the headscarf would not be tolerated because the visible wearing of political, philosophical or religious signs was contrary to the position of neutrality G4S adopted in its contacts with its customers.

On 12 May 2006, after a period of absence from work due to sickness, Ms Achbita notified her employer that she would be returning to work on 15 May and that she would in future be wearing the Islamic headscarf. On 29 May 2006, the G4S works council approved an amendment to the workplace regulations, which came into force on 13 June 2006. These provided that 'employees are prohibited, in the workplace, from wearing any visible signs of their political, philosophical or religious beliefs and/or from engaging in any observance of such belief. On 12 June 2006, Ms Achbita was dismissed because of her continuing insistence on wearing the Islamic headscarf at work. She challenged that dismissal in the Belgian Courts.

The European Court of Justice has ruled that companies can ban employees from wearing the Islamic headscarf, but only as part of prohibitions including other religious and political symbols.

The Court therefore concludes that the prohibition on wearing an Islamic headscarf, which arises from an internal rule of a private undertaking prohibiting the visible wearing of any political, philosophical or religious sign in the workplace, does not constitute direct discrimination based on religion or belief within the meaning of the directive.

By contrast, such a prohibition may constitute indirect discrimination if it is established that the apparently neutral obligation it imposes results, in fact, in persons adhering to a particular religion or belief being put at a particular disadvantage. However, such indirect discrimination may be objectively justified by a legitimate aim, such as the pursuit by the employer, in its relations with its customers, of a policy of political, philosophical and religious neutrality, provided that the means of achieving that aim are appropriate and necessary¹⁵.

The case concerning to a the complaint of a French national, who was a practising Islam, that she is no longer allowed to wear the full-face veil in public following the entry into

¹⁴ Writ Petition No. 26841 of 2006, The High Court of Judicature, Madras 7th Sept 2006

¹⁵ Judgments in Cases C-157/15 Achbita, Centrum voor Gelijkheid van kansen en voor racismebestrijding v G4S Secure Solutions, and C-188/15 Bougnaoui and Association de défense des droits de l'homme (ADDH) v Micropole Univers; Court of Justice of the European Union, Press Release No 30/17 Luxembourg, 14 March 2017

force, on 11 April 2011, of a law prohibiting the concealment of one's face in public places (Law no. 2010-1192 of 11 October 2010).

The Court emphasized that respect for the conditions of "living together" was a legitimate aim for the measure at issue and that, particularly as the State had a lot of room for man oeuvre ("a wide margin of appreciation") as regards this general policy question on which there were significant differences of opinion, the ban imposed by the Law of 11 October 2010 did not breach the Convention¹⁶.

In another Case the U.S. Supreme Court ruled in favour of a Muslim woman who sued for discrimination after being denied a sales job at age of 17 at an Abercrombie & Fitch Co. clothing store in Oklahoma because she wore a head scarf for religious reasons. In an 8-1 decision in the important religious rights case, the Court backed Samantha Elauf, who had been rejected under Abercrombie's sales staff "look policy" after coming to her job interview wearing the head scarf, or hijab¹⁷.

Justice Scalia, writing for seven justices, said Ms. Elauf did not have to make a specific request for a religious accommodation to obtain relief under title VII of the Civil Rights Act of 1964, which prohibits religious discrimination in hiring. Title VII forbids adverse employment decisions made with a forbidden motive. Further Justice Scalia observed, "*whether this motive derives from actual knowledge, a well-founded suspicion or merely a hunch.*" Justice Scalia elaborated on this point obiter dicta as; "*An employer may not make an applicant's religious practice, confirmed or otherwise, a factor in employment decisions.*"

CONCLUSION

The relationship between religion and dress code is the crux of the legal dispute. In *His Holiness Srimad Perarulala Ethiraja Ramanuja Jeeyar Swami, etc. v. State of Tamil Nadu*¹⁸ the Hon'ble Supreme Court held that the right conferred under Articles 25 and 26 of The Constitution of India is not limited to matters of doctrines or beliefs, but it extend to the acts done in pursuance of religion and therefore, the guarantee of rituals, ceremonies and modes of worship are integral parts of religion. But regarding what constitutes as essential part of religion, the Court observed as follows:

"...what constitutes an essential part of a religious or religious practice has to be decided by the courts with reference to the doctrine of a particular religion and include practices which are regarded by the community as a part of its religion."

In *Dr.M.Ismail Faraqui and Others v. Union of India and Others*¹⁹ the Court pointed out the distinction between religious practices and what constitutes an essential and integral part of the religion which runs as follows:

"The right to practice, profess and propagare religion guaranteed under Article 25 of The Constitution does not necessarily include the right to acquire or own or possess property. Similarly, this right does not extend to the right of worship at any and every place of worship"

¹⁶ ECHR 191 (2014) 01.07.2014

¹⁷ Equal Employment Opportunity Commission, Petitioner v. Abercrombie & Fitch Stores, Inc. 575 U. S. (2015)

¹⁸ AIR 1972 SC 1586 : 1972) 2 SCC 11

¹⁹ 1994 (6) SCC 360

so that any hindrance to worship at a particular place per se may infringe the religious freedom guaranteed under Articles 25 and 26 of The Constitution. The protection under Articles 25 and 26 of The Constitution is to religious practice, which forms an essential and integral part of the religion. A practice may be a religious practice, but not an essential and integral part of practice of that religion."

Further in the case of *N.Adithayan v. Travancore Devaswom Board and Others*²⁰ the Court observed:

"The legal position that the protection under Articles 25 and 26 extends a guarantee for rituals and observances, ceremonies and modes of worship which are integral parts of religion and as to what really constitutes an essential part of religion or religious practice has to be decided by the courts with reference to the doctrine of a particular religion or practices regarded as parts of religion, came to be equally firmly laid down."

Recently, our Apex Court reiterated in *Adi Saiva Sivacharyargal Nala Sangam and Ors v. Govt of Tamil Nadu and Another*²¹ that the freedom of religion under Articles 25 and 26 is not only confined to beliefs, but also extends to religious practices. The rights guaranteed under Articles 25 and 26 are circumscribed and are to be enjoyed within the constitutionally permissible parameters. It was observed in para 43 as follows:

"Often occasions will arise when it may become necessary to determine whether a belief or a practice claimed and asserted is a fundamental part of the religious practice of a group or denomination making such a claim before embarking upon the required adjudication. A decision on such claims becomes the duty of the Constitutional Court. It is neither an easy nor an enviable task that the courts are called to perform. Performance of such tasks is not enjoined in the court by virtue of any ecclesiastical jurisdiction conferred on it but in view of its role as the Constitutional arbitrator. Any apprehension that the determination by the court of an essential religious practice itself negatives the freedoms guaranteed by Articles 25 and 26 will have to be dispelled on the touchstone of constitutional necessity."

Across all religion modest dress code has been prescribed for both man and women. Certain countries have their national dress. Similarly each nation has prescribed specific dress code for defence and other personnel. Lawyers and Doctors do have their dress codes. As I understand, dress code has been prescribed to create a separate identity and hierarchy. Do these dress codes contradict with each other? To my mind, each dress code has its purpose and situations in which they are to be used. If you are a lawyer you are not supposed to come in your religious dress code. It is true that during colonial rule certain Indian regiments were characterized by their religious dress. The mix up between religious dress code and occupations were done during colonial regimes. Today in the globalized world, the relationship between religious dress code and occupations have become obscure. One is free to use his religious dress code in his or her personal and religious domain.

²⁰ 2002 (8) SCC 106, Para 16

²¹ 2016 (2) SCC 725, Para 14